

Modified Plithogenic Sets in Criterion Reduction in Optimal Decisioning on Robotized Technology

Nivetha Martin^{1*}, Gabriel XG Yue², Davron Aslonqulovich Juraev³

¹Department of Mathematics, Arul Anandar College(Autonomous),Karumathur, Tamil Nadu, India,
Post Doctoral Department, International Engineering and Technology Institute; Hong Kong, China
Nivetha.martin710@gmail.com

²Department of Computer Science and Engineering, European University Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus, x.yue@external.euc.ac.cy

³ Scientific Research Center, Baku Engineering University, Baku AZ0102, Azerbaijan,
Department of Mathematical Analysis and Differential Equations, Karshi State University, Karshi180119, Uzbekistan.
juraevdavron12@gmail.com

* Correspondence: Nivetha.martin710@gmail.com

Abstract: Plithogenic sets are primarily characterized as a quintuple of the form (P, a, V, d, c) comprising attributes, attribute values, degrees of appurtenance and contradiction. The decision-making process is quite intricate with conflicting criteria or the attributes. Henceforth, it is essential to minimize the number of criteria to reduce the complexity of decisioning. The research is intended to develop a new approach to handle intricate multi-criteria decision-making problems more effectually, particularly when dealing with conflicting and high dimensional criteria. The objective of this research work is to introduce modified Plithogenic sets to perform criterion reduction based on degrees of contradiction. The proposed method scientifically examines the contradiction among attribute values to find the relative importance of each criterion. The computation of criterion weights facilitates in identifying the core criteria essential for optimal ranking. The proposed approach of criterion reduction using modified Plithogenic sets is illustrated in the decisioning of robotized technology. The performance of the proposed model is compared with neutrosophic based Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to validate its robustness and consistency. The efficacy of the developed method of criterion reduction is validated with other most commonly methods of determining criterion weights. The newly introduced approach is more efficient in handling any number of criteria belonging to both benefit and cost category. Also, the contradiction degrees based on the cognition of human experts may result in few variations is identified as the limitation of the proposed approach.

Keywords: Modified Plithogenic set, Criterion Reduction, Degrees of Contradiction, Decision Making, Robotized Technology

1. Introduction

Robotized technology in industries is characterized as the integration of robotic systems to enhance business efficiency. The industrial sectors of this digital era are robotizing their functional framework with advanced technology to adapt to dynamic environments. Automation in the production process, robotic assistance, and Cobots as coworkers are embedded in industries to

promote operational efficiency and improve overall productivity. Optimal decision-making in robotized technology is essential for building a more effective, sustainable, and smart system. However, choosing robotized technology involves complex and challenging criteria. It is necessary to resolve this decision-making problem by leveraging resilient and comprehensive decision models.

In general, a multi-criteria decision-making framework intends to choose the optimum alternative subjected to conflicting criteria. The multi-criteria decision-making models are formulated to serve two purposes: computing criterion weight and ranking the alternatives. Decision-making becomes a simple task when the decisioning circumstance is deterministic in nature. However, in reality, it is constrained by uncertainty, impreciseness, and indeterminacy. Decision models with different representations—fuzzy, intuitionistic, and neutrosophic—are formulated to solve this challenge. Zadeh [1] introduced fuzzy sets with representations of membership values belonging to $[0,1]$. Atanassov [2] extended fuzzy sets to intuitionistic fuzzy sets of the form $[0,1]^2$, which include both membership and non-membership values. Smarandache [3] further extended these representations to neutrosophic sets of the form $[0,1]^3$ comprising truth, indeterminacy, and falsity values. However, there is a need for more generalized representations to accommodate all these forms to design comprehensive decision models. To achieve this, Smarandache evolved a more generalized form of sets called Plithogenic sets [4].

Plithogenic sets are extensively applied in constructing multi-criteria decision-making models. A plithogenic set is basically a quintuple of the form (P, a, V, d, c) , with set P , attribute a , set of attribute values V , degree of appurtenance d , and degree of contradiction c . This fundamental plithogenic set is then developed into septuple extended plithogenic sets of the form $(P, a, V, D_c, D_d, R_c, R_d)$, considering both dominant (D) and recessive attributes (R). Furthermore, the septuple form of extended plithogenic sets is then developed into Generalized Plithogenic Sets, which are 9-tuples of the form $(P, a, V, D_c, D_d, R_c, R_d, S_c, S_d)$. The generalized plithogenic sets consider dominant (D), recessive (R), and satisfactory (S) attribute values to reflect realistic decision-making situations. Plithogenic sets and their extended versions are applied in developing multi-criteria decision-making models only to rank the alternatives. However, these different versions of plithogenic sets are not widely applied in computing criterion weights [5].

Generally, in traditional plithogenic models, only the degrees of appurtenance are usually considered in criterion computations. This same procedure is also followed in the decision-making models based on the representations of fuzzy, intuitionistic, and neutrosophic sets. To the best of our knowledge in the literature, it is found that contradiction-based plithogenic decision-making models are not widely applied in computing criterion weights. The criterion fixation is a crucial step in ranking the alternatives. However, in practice, it is not always possible to obtain complete information or data description of the criteria. Decision-makers are often constrained to handle imprecise and partial information, which further adds complexity to decision-making. To resolve such challenges, the authors propose modified plithogenic sets to determine the core criteria for ranking the alternatives. We prefer plithogenic sets as these sets are characterized as more generalized representations of attributes. Also, these representations, involving more human

cognition, make the proposed criterion reduction approach based on modified plithogenic sets more robust, novel, and time-effective.

On the other hand, the proposed framework based on modified plithogenic sets also addresses the following research questions:

- What is the need for evolving modified plithogenic sets to determine the criterion weights?
- Why should the decision-makers consider the degrees of contradiction in criterion reduction?
- In what ways is the proposed approach effective in comparison with the existing criterion weight computing methods?

The remaining contents of this work are structured into the following segments: The literature review is presented in Section 2. The conceptualization of modified plithogenic sets is discussed in Section 3. The application of the proposed approach is demonstrated in Section 4. Section 5 discusses the efficacy of the results, and the last section concludes the work with future research directions.

2. State of Art of Related Works

This section elicits the related works on the applications of Plithogenic sets in multi-criteria decision-making and states the applications of multi-criteria decision-making methods in robot selection. Furthermore, this section also identifies the research gaps and presents the novel contributions of this research.

Smarandache conceptualized Plithogenic sets in 2018 as a generalization of crisp, fuzzy, intuitionistic, and neutrosophic sets. Plithogenic sets are more robust and effective in handling attributes and attribute values. The construction of these sets is more flexible and suitable for dealing with complex and conflicting criteria. Researchers have integrated Plithogenic representations with multi-criteria decision-making methods to evolve a more adaptable decision-making framework.

Basset et al. [6] discussed a Plithogenic-based decision approach to evaluate the financial performance of manufacturing industries. Huang and Ju [7] applied it in determining the effectiveness of blended teaching quality. Yang et al. [8] employed it in evaluating construction projects. Li et al. [9] utilized it in the comprehensive evaluation of green construction projects. Grida [10] designed a novel Plithogenic model to assess the functioning of IoT-based supply chains. Sudha et al. [11] employed combined Plithogenic hypersoft sets in supplier selection. Fatukasi and Adebisi [12] used it to make optimal decisions on cryptocurrency investments.

On the other hand, the method of TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) has been integrated with Plithogenic sets to enhance the

efficacy of the combined decision method. Ahmad et al. [13] applied Plithogenic-based hypersofts in TOPSIS decision-making for mobile selection. Sankar et al. [14] employed it in COVID-19 decision-making. Liu et al. [15] utilized it in assessing the competency of quality education. Martin [16] leveraged Plithogenic SWARA-TOPSIS (Step-wise Weight Assessment Ratio Analysis) in food processing industries. Devi and Yamini [17] applied Neutrosophic Pythagorean Plithogenic hypersoft sets in school selection.

Afzal et al. [18] employed an N-framed Plithogenic fuzzy hypersoft set and extended NR-TOPSIS in faculty evaluation. Basset and Mohamed [19] developed a Plithogenic TOPSIS-CRITIC (CRiteria Importance Through Intercriteria Correlation) model for supply risk management. Ozcil et al. [20] developed a Plithogenic MAIRCA (Multi-Attributive Ideal-Real Comparative Analysis) integrated model. Sudha et al. [21] applied Plithogenic CRITIC-MAIRCA in ranking feasible livestock feeding stuffs. Sudha et al. [22] employed Plithogenic MACBETH-MAIRCA (Measuring Attractiveness by a Categorical Based Evaluation Technique) in selecting strategies for promoting environmental sustainability. Xing et al. [23] used the Plithogenic RAM (Root Assessment Method) decision approach to determine the performance of concrete structures.

For better understanding, the above related works are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Applications of Plithogenic Decision Making

Authors & Year	Nature of Plithogenic Decision Making	Application	Ranking of Alternatives
Abdel-Basset & Mohamed (2020)	Plithogenic TOPSIS-CRITIC	Sustainable supply chain risk management	✓
Abdel-Basset et al. (2020)	Integrated Plithogenic MCDM	Financial performance evaluation of manufacturing industries	✓
Ahmad et al. (2020)	Plithogenic Hypersoft under Fuzzy Neutrosophic	General MCDM in fuzzy-neutrosophic environment	✓
Grida et al. (2020)	Plithogenic MCDM	IoT-based supply chain performance evaluation	✓
Sankar et al.	Plithogenic TOPSIS	COVID-19	✓

(2020)		decision-making	
Özçil et al. (2020)	Plithogenic MAIRCA	General MCDM problems	✓
Martin (2021)	Plithogenic SWARA-TOPSIS	Food processing methods	✓
Sudha et al. (2022)	Plithogenic CRITIC-MAIRCA	Livestock feeding stuffs	✓
Sudha et al. (2023)	MACBETH-MAIRCA Plithogenic	Strategies for extended producer responsibility (EPR)	✓
Fatukasi & Adebisi (2024)	Plithogenic Hypersoft	Cryptocurrency investment decisions	✓
Afzal et al. (2024)	N-framed Plithogenic Fuzzy Hypersoft Set & NR-TOPSIS	Intelligent faculty evaluation and ranking	✓
Sudha et al. (2024)	Combined Plithogenic Hypersoft	Supplier selection	✓
Devi & Yamini (2025)	Neutrosophic Pythagorean Plithogenic Hypersoft TOPSIS	School selection for parents	✓
Huang & Yu (2025)	Integrated Plithogenic MCDM	College English blended teaching quality evaluation	✓
Liu et al. (2025a)	Integrated Plithogenic MCDM	Green construction evaluation	✓
Yang et al. (2025a)	Plithogenic MCDM	Credit evaluation in construction bidding	✓
Xing et al. (2025)	Plithogenic-RAM	Seismic performance of high-rise structures	✓

Liu et al. (2025b)	Plithogenic TOPSIS	Evaluation of dual-qualified teachers	✓
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The aforementioned literature on Plithogenic applications clearly demonstrates the multitude of ways in which Plithogenic decision-making methods are used to derive optimum solutions. It is also observed that these methods are primarily applied only for the ranking of alternatives.

On the other hand, multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methods are also widely applied in the optimal selection of robots. To mention a few, Yufka and Ozdemir [24] applied the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) in combination with TOPSIS and ELECTRE (Elimination and Choice Expressing the Reality); Singh et al. [25] employed AHP and TOPSIS; Umar et al. [26] leveraged a Fuzzy AHP and TOPSIS approach; Garg et al. [27] utilized Fuzzy SWARA (Fuzzy Step-wise Weight Assessment Ratio Analysis) and the Fuzzy CoCoSo (Combined Compromise Solution) to evaluate robots used in the automobile industry; Sathiya et al. [28] employed the technique of ISM-AHP; and Gamal and Mohamed [29] applied the MOORA (Multi-Objective Optimization on the Basis of Ratio Analysis) method.

In these works, various MCDM methods are employed for both computing criterion weights and ranking the alternatives. In most cases, the AHP method is used to determine the weights of the criteria through a pairwise comparison approach involving human cognition.

2.1 Research Gaps and Contributions

From the above-described works, the following lacunae and research gaps are identified:

- Plithogenic-based multi-criteria decision-making methods are predominantly used only for ranking the alternatives.
- Plithogenic operators and Plithogenic-based functions, which primarily consider only appurtenance degrees, are applied in determining aggregate values.
- Plithogenic-based MCDM approaches have not yet been applied in robot selection.
- To the best of our knowledge, no new decision-making methods based on Plithogeny have been developed.

These research gaps have motivated the authors to evolve a novel Plithogenic-based decision-making approach with the following characteristics:

- Introduction of modified Plithogenic sets with a structured framework to determine criterion weights.
- Incorporation of contradiction degrees in the weight computation process.
- Development of a more flexible, comprehensive, and dynamic decision-making system using Plithogenic sets.
- Application of the proposed model to a real-world problem selecting core criteria in robot selection and extending its applicability to other intricate industrial decision-making contexts.

3. Conceptualization of Modified Plithogenic Sets in Criterion Reduction

3.1 Origin and Development of Modified Plithogenic Sets

This section describes the need of developing the modified Plithogenic sets and elicits the structure of this newly formulated sets.

Plithogenic sets are basically characterized as a quintuple of the form (P, a, V, d, c) where P is the set, a is the attribute, V is the set of attribute values, d is the degree of appurtenance and c is the degree of contradiction.

i.e $d : P \times V \rightarrow P([0,1]^j)$, $j=1,2,3$ and $c : V \times V \rightarrow [0,1]$.

Plithogenic sets are classified as fuzzy if $j=1$, intuitionistic if $j=2$ and neutrosophic if $j=3$. The Plithogenic set is characterized based only on dominant attribute values. Then these sets are further modified into Extended Plithogenic sets considering both dominant and recessive attribute values. The representation is of the form $(P, a, V, d_D, c_D, d_R, c_R)$. In this case, d_D and c_D are with respect to dominant attribute values. Also, d_R and c_R are with respect to recessive attribute values.

Here, $d_D, d_R : P \times V \rightarrow P([0,1]^j)$, $j=1,2,3$ and $c_D, c_R : V \times V \rightarrow [0,1]$.

On other hand, these representations shall be further put into the form of Generalized Plithogenic sets of the form $(P, a, V, d_D, c_D, d_R, c_R, d_S, c_S)$. In this case, three attribute values namely dominant, recessive and satisfactory are considered. The dominant attribute values are extreme positives and recessive attribute values are extreme negatives. Hence in practical application, there is a need for another mediocre like attribute value to set a balance between these extreme attribute values. These three kinds of Plithogenic forms are applied in decision making in integration with multi-criteria decision-making methods to find only the ranking of the alternatives. However, these representations may not be applied directly in finding the criterion weights as these forms deal more with attribute values rather than attributes. But, to find the criterion weights, it is sufficient to consider only the attributes. In general, the procedure of criterion computing method primarily deals only with attributes and their pairwise comparisons. Hence it is essential to modify the Plithogenic sets with different assumptions of contradiction degrees to determine the criterion weights.

3.2 Modified Plithogenic Sets

The Plithogenic set is customized into the form (P, A_B, A_C, c) , Where P is the set, A_B is the set of benefit attributes or criteria, A_C is the set of cost attributes and c is the degree of contradiction considered between the attributes with the following considerations.

$C(A_i, A_j) = 1$, if the A_i belongs to A_B and A_j belongs to A_C

$C(A_j, A_k) = 0$ if A_j and A_k belong to A_C , also both A_j and A_k are not dominant.

$C(A_l, A_m) = 0$ if A_l and A_m belongs to A_B , also both A_l and A_m are not dominant.

3.3 Steps Involved in Criterion Reduction using Modified Plithogenic Sets.

The procedure involved in this proposed approach is similar to the steps followed in criterion weight computing methods of multi-criteria decision making. However, this newly developed approach is base on contradiction degrees and this approach will alleviate the challenges in dealing intricate criteria and ambiguity.

Step 1 : Construction of Contradiction Matrix

The attribute set say A_B and A_C are constructed. The contradiction degrees between the criteria or the attributes of benefit category and cost category are determined based on the opinion of the experts. The contradiction matrix of the below form is framed.

	A_{B1}	A_{B2}	A_{Bm}	A_{C1}	A_{C2}	A_{Cn}
A_B 1	0	$C(A_B$ 1, $A_{B2})$	$C(A_{B1},$ $A_{Bm})$	$C(A_{B1}$, $A_{C1})$	$C(A_{B1},$ $A_{C2})$	$C(A_{B1}$, $A_{Cn})$
A_B 2	$C(A_{B1},$ $A_{B2})$	0	$C(A_{B2},$ $A_{Bm})$	$C(A_{B2}$, $A_{C1})$	$C(A_{B2},$ $A_{C2})$	$C(A_{B2}$, $A_{Cn})$
⋮	0
⋮	0
A_B m	$C(A_{B1},$ $A_{Bm})$	$C(A_B$ 2, $A_{Bm})$	0	$C(A_B$ m, $A_{C1})$	$C(A_{Bm},$ $A_{C2})$	$C(A_B$ m, $A_{Cn})$
A_C 1	$C(A_{C1},$ $A_{B1})$	$C(A_C$ 1, $A_{B2})$	0	$C(A_C$ 1, $A_{Cn})$
A_C 2	$C(A_{C2},$ $A_{B1})$	$C(A_C$ 2, $A_{B2})$	0	$C(A_C$ 2, $A_{Cn})$
⋮	0
⋮	0

					
A_{Cn}	$C(A_{Cn}, A_{B1})$	$C(A_{Cn}, A_{B2})$	0

Step 2: Normalization of the Contradiction Matrix

The values in the contradiction matrix are normalized by dividing each element in the matrix by its respective column sum.

	A_{B1}	A_{B2}	A_{Bm}	A_{C1}	A_{C2}	A_{Cn}
A_{B1}	0	$C(A_{B1}, A_{B2})$	$C(A_{B1}, A_{Bm})$	$C(A_{B1}, A_{C1})$	$C(A_{B1}, A_{C2})$	$C(A_{B1}, A_{Cn})$
A_{B2}	$C(A_{B1}, A_{B2})$	0	$C(A_{B2}, A_{Bm})$	$C(A_{B2}, A_{C1})$	$C(A_{B2}, A_{C2})$	$C(A_{B2}, A_{Cn})$
:	0
:	0
A_{Bm}	$C(A_{B1}, A_{Bm})$	$C(A_{B2}, A_{Bm})$	0	$C(A_{Bm}, A_{C1})$	$C(A_{Bm}, A_{C2})$	$C(A_{Bm}, A_{Cn})$
A_{C1}	$C(A_{C1}, A_{B1})$	$C(A_{C1}, A_{B2})$	0	$C(A_{C1}, A_{Cn})$
A_{C2}	$C(A_{C2}, A_{B1})$	$C(A_{C2}, A_{B2})$	0	$C(A_{C2}, A_{Cn})$
:	0
:	0
A_{Cn}	$C(A_{Cn}, A_{B1})$	$C(A_{Cn}, A_{B2})$	0
Aggregate Row Sum	$\sum A_{B1}$	$\sum A_{B2}$	$\sum A_{Bm}$	$\sum A_{C1}$	$\sum A_{C2}$	$\sum A_{Cn}$

The normalized matrix $N = [r_{ij}]$ is determined and it is presented in the below form

	A_{B1}	A_{B2}	A_{Bm}	A_{C1}	A_{C2}	A_{Cn}
A_{B1}	0	r_{12}	r_{1n}
A_{B2}	0
\vdots	0
\vdots	0
A_{Bm}	0
A_{C1}	0
A_{C2}	0
\vdots	0
\vdots	0
A_{Cn}	r_{n1}	r_{n2}	r_{n3}	0

Step 3: Computation of the Criterion weights

The row sum of the normalized matrix is determined say $\sum r_{ij}$ and the criterion weights of each of the attributes or criteria is computed by $\frac{\sum r_{ij}}{n}$, where n is the number of attribute or criteria considered.

Step 4: Consistency Test

The consistency of the criterion weights is determined by finding the Coefficient of Variation (CV). i.e $CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu}$. If the calculated value of CV is < 0.3 , then the criterion weights computed are considered to be consistent.

The reason for fixing the threshold of CV to be less than 0.3 is grounded from both the methodological rationale and empirical practice of multi-criteria decision making. Coefficient of

variation is generally defined as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean of the criterion weights. Also, CV below 0.3 indicates less variability of the criterion weights and are more relatively balanced. This is specifically observed in the consistency check of weighting methods such as Analytical Hierarchy Process and Entropy-based weighting. Literature such as Tzeng and Huang [30] and other studies in fuzzy based MCDM frameworks recommend low CV thresholds which are typically less than 0.3. These CV values ensure that the expert judgments reflect consensus and do not consist of any instability or bias into the decision process. Thus, using $CV < 0.3$ as a consistency check is a widely accepted heuristic. This certainly facilitates in handling multiple conflicting criteria.

3.4 Illustration

Let us understand with a simple illustration in supplier selection. The attributes that are considered in general are Reliability, Cost, Flexibility, Lead time, Quality. The benefit criteria are Reliability, Flexibility and Quality. On other hand the cost criteria are Cost and Lead Time. In traditional Plithogenic sets, the attribute values subjected to each of the attributes are considered, also the contradiction degrees are assumed between the attribute values. However, in this modified version the attributes or the criteria are grouped in to the sets of benefit and cost criteria. The contradiction degrees are determined by comparing one attribute with another and a matrix comprising all the contradiction degrees is constructed.

Construction of Contradiction Matrix

Let $A_B = \{ \text{Reliability, Flexibility, Quality} \}$ and $A_C = \{ \text{Cost, Lead Time} \}$. Let us assume Quality as the dominant attribute or the criteria under benefit category. Also, Cost is assumed to dominant attribute under cost category. Based on the Experts, let us consider, $c(\text{Quality, Reliability}) = 1/3$, $c(\text{Quality, Flexibility}) = 2/3$, $c(\text{Cost, Lead time}) = 1/2$.

Let us formulate a matrix considering the contradiction degrees between the attributes of both the category.

	Reliability	Flexibility	Quality	Cost	Lead Time
Reliability	0	0	1/3	1	1
Flexibility	0	0	2/3	1	1
Quality	1/3	2/3	0	1	1
Cost	1	1	1	0	1/2
Lead Time	1	1	1	1/2	0

Normalization of the Matrix

Followed by this construction of matrix, this matrix is normalized.

	Reliability	Flexibility	Quality	Cost	Lead Time
Reliability	0	0	0.111111	0.285714	0.285714
Flexibility	0	0	0.222222	0.285714	0.285714
Quality	0.142857	0.25	0	0.285714	0.285714

Cost	0.428571	0.375	0.333333	0	0.142857
Lead Time	0.428571	0.375	0.333333	0.142857	0

Computation of the Criterion Weights

The aggregate means values of each of the criteria is calculated row wise

Criteria/Attribute	Aggregate Values	Criterion Weights
Reliability	0.68254	0.136508
Flexibility	0.793651	0.15873
Quality	0.964286	0.192857
Cost	1.279762	0.255952
Lead Time	1.279762	0.255952

From the above values, the decision makers shall decide the most significant criteria belonging to either of the benefit and cost category. Among the benefit criteria, quality is more significant followed by flexibility and reliability. On other hand, both the attributes of cost category are significant.

Consistency Check

It is essential to perform the test for checking the consistency of the criterion weights. The Coefficient of Variation (CV) is computed.

$$\text{i.e } CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu}$$

On calculating, we obtain $\mu = 0.2$, $\sigma = 0.0526$ and $CV = 0.263$.

Since a $CV < 0.3$ is generally considered acceptable consistency. Hence, the criterion weights are consistent.

4. Application of Modified Plithogenic Sets in Criterion Reduction of Selecting Robotized Technology.

In this section, the proposed modified Plithogenic set is applied for criterion reduction, with special reference to robotized technology. As discussed in the previous sections, industrial frameworks are increasingly embracing robotic technology and integrating advanced models into their operational functionality. Manufacturing sectors, regardless of their production scale, are incorporating automation technologies that are feasible within their financial capabilities.

However, decision-makers are often confronted with the challenge of selecting the optimal criteria for choosing appropriate robotized technologies. Criterion reduction becomes the primary and essential step in this process, as it is necessary to explore and evaluate all possible criteria before identifying the most optimal set.

4.1 Problem Description

Let us consider a company which has decided to adopt a robotized technology for the ease of work. In general, from the literature it is found that the criteria such as Performance, Flexibility, Purchase Cost, Maintenance cost, Working Accuracy, Load Capacity, Energy Assumption are generally considered. However, in any decisioning problem it is essential to explore all the possible criteria to make a more comprehensive decision on criterion reduction. The possible 20 criteria and description are presented in the Table 2.

Table 2 Description of the Criteria

Criteria	Description
Cost	Expenditure of initial investment and maintenance
Performance	Functionality of the technology
Flexibility	Adaptive nature to various environments
Scalability	Scaling of operations
Integration	Compatibility with other operating systems
Safety	Minimal risks with more compliance to standards
Energy Efficiency	Efficacy in resource optimization
Ease of Use	User friendliness in operations
Durability	Degree of resistance to external factors
Technical Support	Easy availability of functional parts
Precision	Working with high accuracy
Payload Capacity	Ability to handle heavy load
Mobility	Ease of navigation and motility
Environment Compatibility	Adapting to specific circumstances
Return on Investment	Profit earned from the investment
Customization	Potential to modify based on the requirements
Reliability	Consistency in utility
Compliance	Adherence to the general standards
Automation Level	Ability to perform task with minimum supervision
Innovation Potential	Competency in accommodating advanced technology

The categorization of the criteria into benefit and cost is tabulated in Table 3

Table 3 Categorization of Criteria

Benefit Criteria A_B	Cost Criteria A_C
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Performance (A_{B1})	Initial Investment (A_{C1})
Flexibility(A_{B2})	Maintenance Costs (A_{C2})
Scalability (A_{B3})	Operational Costs (A_{C3})
Integration(A_{B4})	Training Requirements (A_{C4})
Safety (A_{B5})	Downtime and Repair Costs (A_{C5})
Energy Efficiency (A_{B6})	
Ease of Use (A_{B7})	
Precision (A_{B8})	
Payload Capacity (A_{B9})	
Mobility (A_{B10})	
Environment Compatibility (A_{B11})	
Return on Investment (A_{B12})	
Customization (A_{B13})	
Reliability (A_{B14})	
Innovation Potential (A_{B15})	

Let us discuss the problem under two cases.

Case (i)

Let us assume the dominant benefit criteria is Performance (A_{B1}). The dominant cost criteria is Initial Investment (A_{C1}). The contradiction degrees between the benefit attributes and cost attributes are presented as follows based on the perception of the experts. $C(A_{B1}, A_{B2}) = 1/15$, $C(A_{B1}, A_{B3})=2/15$, $C(A_{B1}, A_{B4})=3/15$, $C(A_{B1}, A_{B5}) = 4/15$, $C(A_{B1}, A_{B6}) = 5/15$, $C(A_{B1}, A_{B7}) = 6/15$, $C(A_{B1}, A_{B8}) = 7/15$, $C(A_{B1}, A_{B9}) = 8/15$, $C(A_{B1}, A_{B10}) = 9/15$, $C(A_{B1}, A_{B11}) = 10/15$, $C(A_{B1}, A_{B12}) = 11/15$, $C(A_{B1}, A_{B13}) = 12/15$, $C(A_{B1}, A_{B14}) = 13/15$, $C(A_{B1}, A_{B15}) = 14/15$.

On other hand $C(A_{C1}, A_{C2})=1/5$, $C(A_{C1}, A_{C2})=2/15$, $C(A_{C1}, A_{C2})=3/15$, $C(A_{C1}, A_{C2})=4/15$

Let us apply the procedure discussed in section 3 considering a single expert’s opinion. The contradiction matrix between the criteria is thus obtained.

	A _{B1}	A _{B2}	A _{B3}	A _{B4}	A _{B5}	A _{B6}	A _{B7}	A _{B8}	A _{B9}	A _{B10}	A _{B11}	A _{B12}	A _{B13}	A _{B14}	A _{B15}	A _{C1}	A _{C2}	A _{C3}	A _{C4}	A _{C5}
A _{B1}	0	$\frac{1}{15}$	$\frac{2}{15}$	$\frac{3}{15}$	$\frac{4}{15}$	$\frac{5}{15}$	$\frac{6}{15}$	$\frac{7}{15}$	$\frac{8}{15}$	$\frac{9}{15}$	$\frac{10}{15}$	$\frac{11}{15}$	$\frac{12}{15}$	$\frac{13}{15}$	$\frac{14}{15}$	1	1	1	1	1
A _{B2}	$\frac{1}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
A _{B3}	$\frac{2}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1

A_{B4}	$\frac{3}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
A_{B5}	$\frac{4}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
A_{B6}	$\frac{5}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
A_{B7}	$\frac{6}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
A_{B8}	$\frac{7}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
A_{B9}	$\frac{8}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
A_{B10}	$\frac{9}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
A_{B11}	$\frac{10}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
A_{B12}	$\frac{11}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
A_{B13}	$\frac{12}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
A_{B14}	$\frac{13}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
A_{B15}	$\frac{14}{15}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
A_{C1}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	$\frac{1}{5}$	$\frac{2}{5}$	$\frac{3}{5}$	$\frac{4}{5}$
A_{C2}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	$\frac{1}{5}$	0	0	0	0
A_{C3}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	$\frac{2}{5}$	0	0	0	0
A_{C4}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	$\frac{3}{5}$	0	0	0	0
A_{C5}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	$\frac{4}{5}$	0	0	0	0

The above matrix is normalized using step 2.

	A B1	A B2	A B3	A B4	A B5	A B6	A B7	A B8	A B9	A B10	A B11	A B12	A B13	A B14	A B15	A C1	A C2	A C3	A C4	A C5
Λ_{B1}			0. 0 2	0. 0 3	0. 0 5		0. 0 7	0. 0 8	0. 0 9											
		0.0 13 15 0	5 9 7 4	8 4 6 2	0 6 3 3	0 6 2 5	4 0 7 4	5 3 6 6	6 3 8 6	0.1 07 14 3	0.1 17 64 7	0.1 27 90 7	0.1 37 93 1	0.1 47 72 7	0.1 57 30 3	0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91
Λ_{B2}	0. 00 55 56															0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91
Λ_{B3}	0. 01 11 11															0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91
Λ_{B4}	0. 01 66 67															0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91
Λ_{B5}	0. 02 22 22															0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91
Λ_{B6}	0. 02 77 78															0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91
Λ_{B7}	0. 03 33 33															0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91
Λ_{B8}	0. 03 88 89															0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91
Λ_{B9}	0.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

	04 44 44															66 66 7	58 82 4	64 93 5	64 10 3	632 91	
Λ_{B10}	0. 05	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91	
Λ_{B11}	0. 05 55 56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91	
Λ_{B12}	0. 06 11 11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91	
Λ_{B13}	0. 06 66 67	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91	
Λ_{B14}	0. 07 22 22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91	
Λ_{B15}	0. 07 77 78	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0 66 66 7	0.0 58 82 4	0.0 64 93 5	0.0 64 10 3	0.0 632 91	
Λ_{C1}	0. 08 33 33	0.1 97 36 8	0. 1 9 5	0. 1 9 0	0. 1 8 7	0. 1 8 5	0. 1 8 5	0. 1 8 7	0. 1 8 3	0. 1 9 2	0.1 78 57 1	0.1 76 47 1	0.1 74 41 9	0.1 72 41 4	0.1 70 45 5	0.1 68 53 9	0.0 11 76 0	0.0 25 97 5	0.0 38 46 4	0.0 506 2	33
Λ_{C2}	0. 08 33 33	0.1 97 36 8	0. 1 9 4	0. 1 9 2	0. 1 8 8	0. 1 8 8	0. 1 8 5	0. 1 8 2	0. 1 8 0	0. 1 9 1	0.1 78 57 1	0.1 76 47 1	0.1 74 41 9	0.1 72 41 4	0.1 70 45 5	0.1 68 53 9	0.0 23 52 0				0

			8	3	8	5	1	9	7											
			0	0	7		8	2	2											
			5	8	3		5	7	3											
Λ_{C3}			0.	0.	0.		0.	0.	0.											
			1	1	1		1	1	1											
			9	9	8	0.	8	8	8											
	0.	0.1	4	2	9	1	5	2	0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1		0.0			
	08	97	8	3	8	8	1	9	7	78	76	74	72	70	68		35			
	33	36	0	0	7	7	8	2	2	57	47	41	41	45	53		29			
	33	8	5	8	3	5	5	7	3	1	1	9	4	5	9	0	4	0	0	0
Λ_{C4}			0.	0.	0.		0.	0.	0.											
			1	1	1		1	1	1											
			9	9	8	0.	8	8	8											
	0.	0.1	4	2	9	1	5	2	0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1		0.0			
	08	97	8	3	8	8	1	9	7	78	76	74	72	70	68		47			
	33	36	0	0	7	7	8	2	2	57	47	41	41	45	53		05			
	33	8	5	8	3	5	5	7	3	1	1	9	4	5	9	0	9	0	0	0
Λ_{C5}			0.	0.	0.		0.	0.	0.											
			1	1	1		1	1	1											
			9	9	8	0.	8	8	8											
	0.	0.1	4	2	9	1	5	2	0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1					
	08	97	8	3	8	8	1	9	7	78	76	74	72	70	68					
	33	36	0	0	7	7	8	2	2	57	47	41	41	45	53					
	33	8	5	8	3	5	5	7	3	1	1	9	4	5	9	0	0	0	0	0

The criterion weights are determined using step 3 and presented in Table 4

Table 4 Criterion Weights

Criteria	Row Sum	Criterion Weights
Λ_{B1}	1.560029	0.078001
Λ_{B2}	0.323375	0.016169
Λ_{B3}	0.32893	0.016447
Λ_{B4}	0.334486	0.016724
Λ_{B5}	0.340041	0.017002
Λ_{B6}	0.345597	0.01728
Λ_{B7}	0.351152	0.017558
Λ_{B8}	0.356708	0.017835

A_{B9}	0.362263	0.018113
A_{B10}	0.367819	0.018391
A_{B11}	0.373375	0.018669
A_{B12}	0.37893	0.018947
A_{B13}	0.384486	0.019224
A_{B14}	0.390041	0.019502
A_{B15}	0.395597	0.01978
A_{C1}	2.761724	0.138086
A_{C2}	2.658421	0.132921
A_{C3}	2.670185	0.133509
A_{C4}	2.68195	0.134098
A_{C5}	2.634891	0.131745

From the criterion weights, the most significant criteria under benefit and cost categories shall be easily determined. Among the benefit criteria, A_{B15} , A_{B14} , A_{B13} are identified to be the core criteria. Among the cost criteria, A_{C2} , A_{C4} , A_{C3} are identified to be significant.

Let us perform consistency test to determine the reliability of the criterion weights. The value of CV is less than 0.3 and it indicates less variability in the results.

Case (ii)

Let us repeat the same problem by considering second expert’s opinion. In this case the dominant

benefit criteria is Flexibility (A_{B2}) and dominant cost criteria is Operational Costs (A_{C3}).

Repeating the same procedure, the criterion weights obtained are presented in Table 5

Table 5 Criterion Weights

Criteria	Row Sum	Criterion Weights
A_{B1}	0.3225	0.016125
A_{B2}	1.55915	0.07796
A_{B3}	0.32805	0.016403
A_{B4}	0.33361	0.01668
A_{B5}	0.33916	0.01696

A_{B6}	0.34472	0.01724
A_{B7}	0.350275	0.01751
A_{B8}	0.355831	0.01779
A_{B9}	0.361386	0.01807
A_{B10}	0.366942	0.01835
A_{B11}	0.372497	0.01862
A_{B12}	0.378053	0.0189
A_{B13}	0.383608	0.01918
A_{B14}	0.389164	0.01946
A_{B15}	0.39472	0.01974
A_{C1}	2.64666	0.13233
A_{C2}	2.65842	0.13292
A_{C3}	2.763118	0.13816
A_{C4}	2.67019	0.13351
A_{C5}	2.68195	0.1341

From the criterion weights, the significant criteria identified under benefit category are A_{B12} , A_{B15} , A_{B14} . Similarly, under cost category, the significant criteria are A_{C3} , A_{C5} and A_{C4} . The same approach shall be followed by assuming dominant benefit and cost criteria.

5. Results and Discussions

The application of modified plithogenic sets in criterion reduction has minimized the challenges in determining the significant criteria. Among the 20 criteria, the significant criteria under benefit and cost category are determined with minimal procedure. The results obtained under two cases are presented in the Table 6.

Table 6 Significant criterion sets

Expert	Dominant Benefit Criteria	Dominant Cost Criteria	Significant Benefit Criterion set	Significant Cost Criterion set
I	A_{B1}	A_{C1}	A_{B15} , A_{B14} , A_{B13}	A_{C2} , A_{C3} , A_{C4}
II	A_{B2}	A_{C3}	A_{B12} , A_{B15} , A_{B14}	A_{C3} , A_{C4} , A_{C5}

The results obtained under two cases are based on the preferences of the decision-makers. If the managerial focuses on performances and initial investments then the criteria that it has to consider under benefit category are Customization (A_{B13}), Reliability (A_{B14}) and Innovation Potential (A_{B15}). Also, with respect to the cost category, Maintenance Costs (A_{C2}), Operational Costs (A_{C3}) and Training Requirements (A_{C4}) are considered.

On other hand if the decision makers prefer or focus on Flexibility(A_{B2}) and Operational Costs (A_{C3}). Then the Return on Investment (A_{B12}), Reliability (A_{B14}) and Innovation Potential (A_{B15}) are to be considered under benefit category. Also, with respect to the cost category, Operational Costs (A_{C3}), Training Requirements (A_{C4}) and Downtime and Repair Costs (A_{C5}) are considered. The reduced criterion set includes the dominant criteria under both the category in addition to these significant criterion sets.

5.1 Comparative Analysis with Neutrosophic AHP

The decision-making problem presented in Section 4 is addressed using the Neutrosophic-based AHP method. This method is chosen because it is commonly applied to determine criterion weights based on relative comparisons among the criteria. However, there are certain challenges encountered when considering all 15 benefit criteria and 6 cost criteria simultaneously. To reduce computation time and improve efficiency, Python libraries are utilized to compute the weights of the criteria. The resulting weights are presented in Table 7.

Table 7 Neutrosophic AHP Criterion Weights

Criterion	Normalized Weight
A_{B1}	0.050811
A_{B2}	0.050388
A_{B3}	0.050887
A_{B4}	0.050757
A_{B5}	0.050696
A_{B6}	0.050812
A_{B7}	0.050238
A_{B8}	0.050362
A_{B9}	0.050279
A_{B10}	0.049818
A_{B11}	0.049821
A_{B12}	0.050174
A_{B13}	0.049813
A_{B14}	0.049331
A_{B15}	0.049528

A_{C1}	0.049586
A_{C2}	0.049434
A_{C3}	0.049282
A_{C4}	0.049212
A_{C5}	0.048771

From Table 7, only negligible differences are observed in the criterion weights. As a result, these values do not effectively support the selection of a significant set of criteria. Additionally, the consideration of nearly 20 criteria introduces computational complexity. There are also no provisions in the previously discussed cases (i) and (ii) to prioritize specific benefit or cost criteria. Furthermore, existing MCDM methods may lack the competence to efficiently handle a large number of criteria, thereby necessitating a new approach to criterion reduction.

5.2 Strengths of the Proposed Approach

The modified Plithogenic sets are more capable and competent in effectively handling conflicting, intricate, and large sets of criteria. This new approach shares similarities with traditional methods for computing criterion weights but differs significantly in its consideration of contradiction degrees. The modified Plithogenic approach based on contradictions stands out as distinct and novel for the following reasons:

• Ability to Handle Conflict and Ambiguity

Conventional weight computation methods typically rely on preferences, correlations, or the assumption of independence among criteria. However, in reality, criteria are often inherently contradictory. For example, cost minimization and quality maximization are naturally conflicting objectives. To address such contradictions, it is crucial to incorporate contradiction degrees, offering a more realistic and practical way to manage complex decision-making systems. In the case of criterion reduction for robotized technology, the criteria classified under benefit and cost categories are often conflicting. This new approach demonstrates greater competence in managing such scenarios.

• Choice of Plithogenic Logic

Plithogenic sets are inherently designed to handle contradiction degrees between attribute values. Therefore, introducing a modified form of these sets to account for contradictions between attributes reflects a progressive shift in soft computing techniques. This innovation opens up new pathways for modelling more realistic and adaptive decision systems.

• Increased Decision Stability

The contradiction matrix provides a foundational structure for enhancing the stability of decisions. The sequential steps employed in the process contribute to forming cohesive decision logic, supported by human expertise. This aspect is particularly critical when dealing with a large number of criteria, ensuring systematic and stable outcomes.

• Flexibility for Diverse Criteria

The proposed approach exhibits high compatibility and adaptability—not only for large sets of criteria but also for mixed-type criteria. For example, in the case of criterion reduction for robotized technology, the criteria span both benefit and cost categories. This approach effectively facilitates the identification of significant criteria within each category, supporting more structured and actionable decisions.

• Reliability and Uniqueness

This approach is unique in its explicit consideration of contradiction degrees, setting it apart from conventional methods such as AHP and Entropy-based models. The reliability of the computed criterion weights is ensured through consistency checks, contributing to the robustness of the decision-making process.

5.3 Limitations and Scope for Enhancement

Despite its strengths, the proposed approach has certain limitations. The objectivity of the results may be compromised due to human intervention in selecting dominant criteria and assigning contradiction degrees. As a result, the outcomes tend to be subjective, relying heavily on human cognition. However, this subjectivity can be viewed positively, as it introduces a nuanced layer of human-centric insight into the decision process. To address concerns about subjectivity and enhance objectivity, a group decision-making strategy can be employed, ensuring a more balanced and consensus-driven evaluation.

Conclusion

This research work proposes a modified Plithogenic set and demonstrates its efficacy in criterion reduction. The newly developed approach can be characterized as a conflict-sensitive mechanism, which aligns effectively with the complexities, uncertainties, and contradictions inherent in real-world decision-making environments. This novel method is highly competent in handling a large number of criteria and is well-substantiated through its application to the criterion reduction of robotized technology. The methodology of the proposed approach is both simple and time-efficient.

The advantages and limitations of this decision-making approach have been thoroughly presented. Notably, this novel method of criterion reduction lays the groundwork for the development of new integrated methods based on contradiction analysis. It also contributes meaningfully to the existing literature on Plithogenic multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM). Additionally, the comparison with neutrosophic AHP exhibits the uniqueness of the proposed approach and its competency in handling a large number of criteria.

The proposed approach may be further enhanced by incorporating group decision-making, where expert opinions are considered for identifying dominant criteria in both benefit and cost categories, as well as for assigning contradiction degrees. Moreover, the dominant criterion framework can be extended by categorizing criteria into dominant, recessive, and satisfactory types. The inclusion of these three poles would contribute to the development of a more comprehensive and realistic decision-making model.

Furthermore, this approach holds potential for integration with machine learning algorithms as a direction for future work, thereby enhancing its adaptability and automation in large-scale, data-driven decision environments.

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Appendix

```
import numpy as np
```

```
import pandas as pd
```

```
# List of criteria (15 Benefit + 5 Cost)
```

```
criteria = [
```

```
    "AB1_Performance", "AB2_Flexibility", "AB3_Scalability", "AB4_Integration",
    "AB5_Safety",
```

```
        "AB6_EnergyEfficiency", "AB7_EaseOfUse", "AB8_Precision",
    "AB9_PayloadCapacity", "AB10_Mobility",
```

```

        "AB11_EnvironmentCompatibility", "AB12_ROI", "AB13_Customization",
"AB14_Reliability", "AB15_InnovationPotential",
        "AC1_InitialInvestment", "AC2_MaintenanceCosts", "AC3_OperationalCosts",
"AC4_TrainingRequirements", "AC5_DowntimeRepairCosts"
    ]
n = len(criteria)

```

Step 1: Generate simulated Neutrosophic Pairwise Comparison Matrices (T, I, F)

```
np.random.seed(42) # For reproducibility
```

```
T = np.ones((n, n)) # Truth matrix, diagonal is 1
```

```
I = np.zeros((n, n)) # Indeterminacy matrix
```

```
F = np.zeros((n, n)) # Falsity matrix
```

Fill upper triangle with random values and infer lower triangle

```
for i in range(n):
```

```
    for j in range(i + 1, n):
```

```
        t = np.round(np.random.uniform(0.5, 0.9), 2) # Truth in [0.5, 0.9]
```

```
        i_val = np.round(np.random.uniform(0.0, 0.3), 2) # Indeterminacy in [0.0, 0.3]
```

```
        f = np.round(1 - t, 2) # Falsity as complement of truth
```

```
        T[i, j] = t
```

```
        I[i, j] = i_val
```

```
        F[i, j] = f
```

```
        T[j, i] = np.round(1 - t, 2)
```

```
        I[j, i] = i_val
```

```
        F[j, i] = t
```

Step 2: Normalize columns for T, I, F

```
T_col_sum = T.sum(axis=0)
```

```
I_col_sum = I.sum(axis=0)
```

```
F_col_sum = F.sum(axis=0)
```

```
T_norm = T / T_col_sum
```

```
I_norm = I / I_col_sum
```

```
F_norm = F / F_col_sum
```

Step 3: Compute average per row (Neutrosophic Weights)

```
T_avg = T_norm.mean(axis=1)
```

```
I_avg = I_norm.mean(axis=1)
F_avg = F_norm.mean(axis=1)

# Step 4: Score function and final normalized weight
scores = (T_avg + (1 - I_avg) + (1 - F_avg)) / 3
normalized_weights = scores / scores.sum()

# Step 5: Store results in DataFrame
df_weights = pd.DataFrame({
    'Criterion': criteria,
    'T_avg': T_avg,
    'I_avg': I_avg,
    'F_avg': F_avg,
    'Score': scores,
    'Normalized_Weight': normalized_weights
})

# Sort by weight
df_weights_sorted = df_weights.sort_values(by="Normalized_Weight",
ascending=False).reset_index(drop=True)

# Optional: Save to CSV
df_weights_sorted.to_csv("neutrosophic_ahp_criterion_weights.csv", index=False)

# Display top 10 criteria
print(df_weights_sorted.head(10))
```

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